

Reaction of rice varieties or cultures to bacterial blight disease.

Variety or culture	Disease severity scale ^a					
	Seedling		Tillering		Boot-leaf	
	Pots	Field	Pots	Field	Pots	Field
BJ1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sigadis	0	0	0	0	1	0
TKM6	1	0	1	0	1	1
ASD5	1	0	1	1	5	5
IR22	1	1	5	3	5	5
IR26	3	1	5	5	5	5
Pankaj	1	1	3	1	3	3
TNI	5	5	7	7	7	7
TNAU7124 (ASD5/IR22)	1	1	1	1	5	3
TNAU15776 (IR20/ASD5)	1	1	1	1	5	3
ASDIS (IR22/IR26)	3	3	7	1	7	7

^a0 = not affected, 9 = highly susceptible.

tribution of resistance by IR22 and IR20 in those two cultivars appears insufficient. ASD15 (IR22/IR26) is also susceptible (see table).

ASD5 has potential resistance until

the tillering stage to the bacterium strain that causes severe damage to most of the improved rice varieties that are known to be bacterial blight resistant. ■

Root knot nematode—*Fusarium* complex in rice under dryland conditions in Brazil

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A root disease complex is affecting rice in the savannas (cerrados) of the states of Goias, Mato Grosso do Sul, and Mato Grosso where dryland rice is extensively grown.

The symptoms on the aboveground parts were retarded growth, reduced tillering, and pale yellow leaves. The symptoms were evident about 25 days after planting and the difference in height between diseased and healthy plants increased with time.

The affected farmers' fields showed light yellow patches of plants exhibiting retarded growth, and some nutritional disorder was generally suspected. But when the plants were pulled out, a black discoloration was seen at the underground basal node where adventitious roots are initiated. This discoloration extended along the mesocotyl, but seldom to the adventitious roots. Examination of transverse sections of the root at the underground basal node of the culm showed discoloration of vascular tissues. Death of the affected plants was,

however, uncommon.

Isolating more than 50 diseased plant samples from different fields yielded 2 distinct species of *Fusarium*. Inoculation tests using diverse isolates showed that one of the two species was highly

Incidence of *Meloidogyne javanica* and *Fusarium* sp. in 12 rice cultivars under upland conditions in Brazil.

Cultivar	Total number of plants	Infected plants ^a (%)	
		<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	<i>M. javanica</i>
Early maturing			
Pratao Precoce (standard)	518	93.71	35.99
Dourado Precoce	402	81.79**	3.49**
IAC 25	303	66.78**	27.31
Medium duration			
IAC 47 (standard)	365	69.86	43.12
Pratao	434	56.32**	40.38
IAC 1246	385	53.18**	38.46
Iguape Redondo	428	46.91**	44.49
Fernandes	294	43.21**	38.67
Amarelao	270	37.23**	62.20**
IAC 5544	312	32.27**	48.27
IRAT 13	261	31.62**	55.77
Bico Ganga	305	29.72**	33.66

^aData presented include combined infection of *Fusarium* and *Meloidogyne*. Mean percentages marked with asterisks are significantly different from the standard checks as judged by t-test at the 1% level of probability.

Evaluation of resistance to rice blast in observation plots of Bagua

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pathogenic. The identification of the pathogenic species is under way.

The incidence of root knot nematode caused by *Meloidogyne javanica* was observed after 75 days of crop growth in the experimental plots at the National Center of Rice and Beans, as well as in some of the farmers' fields affected with *Fusarium*.

Preliminary evaluation of the field incidence in 12 dryland rice cultivars, each grown in plots of 900 m², showed significant differences in the percentage of plants affected by root infection caused by *Fusarium*, root knot nematode, and both root knot and *Fusarium* (see table). While the plants showing galls and egg masses on the roots incited by *M. javanica* had no symptom on the aerial parts, the plants affected with *Fusarium* infection singly or in combination with root knot nematode were retarded in growth and had few tillers.

The root disease complex was commonly found in the second and third year of successive rice cultivations in savannas or in fields where rice is grown in rotation with pasture. ■

Materials selected from rice blast infection beds were tested for resistance to leaf blast (seedling stage) and neck blast (adult stage) in 20-m² observation plots in fields where the incidence of blast was high. Additional information was taken

to identify good sources of resistance.

This report covers material tested in the Experimental Sub-Station Huarangopampa-Bagua (5° 35' lat. S., 78° 30' long. W) in 1978, 1979 and 1980. Of the 17 lines and varieties chosen for each test, 10 were selected from trials in Bagua, Yurimaguas, and Tingo Maria from 1968 through 1978 and the remaining 7 were obtained from IRBN-75, which was tested during 1976 and 1977 in the same 3 sites.

Low natural infection at the seedling stage prevented clear differentiation of the materials for resistance to leaf blast. The severity of the blast attacks at the panicle stage, however, (26% in Minabir 2 in 1978 and 70% in Fanny in 1979 and 1980) made it possible to single out the resistant materials Colombia I, C46-15,

and Tetep. These three varieties kept their resistance to leaf blast over several years and have been the most consistently tolerant in the field.

Colombia I and C46-15 had relatively good yielding potential despite their low tillering capacity. Tetep and C46-15 are tall and have lodging tendencies.

Their poor plant type should be considered if they are to be used as parents. Colombia I also is resistant to the virus disease hoja blanca and is convenient to use as a resistance source in Bagua and Jaen, where blast and hoja blanca are cyclicly epidemic.

A second group of good materials — IR1544-238-2-3, IR1416-1-42-2-3-3, and Tadukan — have shown acceptable agronomic characteristics, but are not as stable in reaction to blast as Colombia

I, C46-15, and Tetep.

IR1544-238-2-3 and IR1416-142-2-3-3 have good yield potential, dwarf plant type, and intermediate reaction to hoja blanca but have shown susceptible reactions to leaf blast. Tadukan has low yield potential, tall plant type, and intermediate reaction to hoja blanca. It has been more consistent in its resistance at both seedling and adult stages.

The rest of the rices tested showed an unstable capacity to withstand the pathogenic variability of the fungus. P545-5-22-3-5-2-2, Carreon, and Dissi Hatif, particularly, gave variable reactions. However, the same variability of the fungus imposed the use of different sources of resistance in the breeding for blast-resistant varieties. ■

Rice materials selected for resistance to *P. oryzae* in infection beds at Yurimaguas, Bagua, and Tingo Maria

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The materials tested in infection beds by the PNA (Rice National Program) consist of rices selected in the breeding program, those tested for blast resistance, PNA promising lines, and those introduced from abroad (International Rice Research Institute, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, etc.). The rices that showed blast resistance after several tests are retested and analyzed for their general reaction, reaction by locality, consistency of reaction, source of resistance used, etc.

This report includes the rices with outstanding performance during the periods 1968-72 and 1974-78, during which more than 16,500 rices were tested. It also includes the best materials in three localities.

In 1968, a strong program for rice varietal improvement started in Peru. In the first testing period (1968-72), most of the blast-resistant rices were materials introduced mainly from IRRI. IR480-5-9-2, IR532, and Tetep were used as res-

istance sources. Their progeny performed well in the second testing period (1974-78).

Of the rices ranked outstanding in the second period, 63% were from Peru, 27% from Colombia, and 10% from IRRI. These rices should be further tested for consistency of blast resistance. Among the selected material, five lines were IR480-5-9-2 derivatives, two were Tetep derivatives, two were PI 184675

derivatives, and one was a Colombia I derivative.

The PNA 12-24 group of resistant lines (6 lines), which are progeny of IR8/ Apura, are especially interesting. During the 1969-72 period in the same test localities, IR8 was moderately resistant to moderately susceptible to blast and Apura was consistently moderately resistant. The latter reaction should be defined and studied carefully. ■

Rice cultivars found resistant during a tungro epidemic

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Tungro virus disease appeared in epidemic form in Bihar in October 1980. Of 150 rice cultivars screened in six trials, only 4 were found highly resistant: IR38, IR2863-38-1, C190-1, and C183-1. BIET 281, Borogar 5, BR 1-91-6, 62-31, 7551 G-5, BR34, BR9, Parwapankh, and 64-117 were tolerant. The susceptible cultivars included Jaya, Pankaj, Biplab, T141, Intan, IET5656, IET6710, IR2050-78-1-3, and Kencanna. ■

Donors of brown spot resistance in the Indian Punjab

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The 570 IET (Initial Evaluation Trial) entries of rice received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project were screened for reaction to brown spot *Helminthosporium oryzae* in the field during 1980 kharif at the PAU Rice Research Substation, Gurdaspur. The entries were grown in 2 rows, 5 m long. Fertilizers were applied at 100-50-50 kg of N, P₂O₅, and K per hectare. The disease was scored by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale, 3 months after transplanting. Two